

TechOceanS Milestone 9 – Technology demonstrated to Stakeholders (Month 48)

Work Packages: 2, 7, 12 and 16

Lead: AquaTT

Due: 30/09/2024

The TechOceanS technologies listed in the table below have been successfully demonstrated to stakeholders as both pilot activities at field sites in PLOCAN and SZN and as data evidence in technology workshops. The results of this analysis are summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1 TechOceanS technologies’ demonstrations

Technology	Relevant Stakeholders	Notes on Demonstrations	TRL assessment
Flexible Fluidics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquaculture (including coastal and offshore finfish and shellfish farms susceptible to Harmful Algal Blooms) • Water services and water quality monitors 	The technology was demonstrated in pilot scale trials and proven to peer researchers in targeted sectors to be of high value for user applications including EIA, Biodiversity Assessment, and fisheries and aquaculture security monitoring (e.g. screening for harmful algal blooms, invasive species, etc.). As a result of these positive tests and feedback, a patent was secured to allow for the further development and commercialisation.	5
RoCSI eDNA sampler	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity and Environmental researchers and impact assessors • Fisheries and marine aquaculture • Conservationists 	The RoCSI system was effectively demonstrated to leading experts in the Atlantic region for biodiversity and ocean observation during field exercises in Plocan’s Gran Canaria testing site at surface towing, surface stationary and at-depth AUV operations. The success of these tests has led to the optioning of the technology for full-scale commercial production with promising potential applications in remote EIA, fishery stock evaluation and oceanic ecosystem health evaluations.	8
Microplastics Sampler	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oceanography, marine biology and water quality researchers • Water quality monitors 	Technology was re-tasked from the pressure balanced eDNA sampler and demonstrated in a representative environment as a complete system capable of autonomous running and monitoring for environmental microplastics. The	6/7

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste water policy stakeholders 	results of this technology test have been labelled as promising by experts on water and waste water policy as well as peer researchers from upcoming and sister projects.	
In situ nucleic acid sensor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental observation institutes, agencies and researchers Conservationists 	Although the TRL has not been advanced, the manufacturing readiness level has been improved as in terms of speed and reliability. Testing at two field trials at partner institutions SZN (Naples, Italy) and IMBB (Crete, Greece) allowed for the successful demonstration of the technology to researchers who are positioned to further advance this technology towards the identified applications.	5/6
Remote Imaging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental observation institutes, agencies and researchers Research funding agencies Oceanic monitors (biodiversity, climate change, fisheries, security, etc.) Ocean physical resource policy makers and monitors 	The workflow and hard-ware for low-bandwidth comms and data compression has been demonstrated in real-world environments using BioCAM on ALR and also Smarty200, at Plocan and at Studland Bay (UK) seagrass (EOV) marine protected areas. The system functioned, demonstrating performance on different hardware directly in those environments that are monitored and administered by the target stakeholder demographic. The positive feedback from these tests has been included in the project Policy roadmap and deemed successful enough to continue exploring expanded test sites.	6
UVP6m Imaging Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oceanographers Marine and maritime physical resource surveyors and monitors (e.g. site surveyors for wind turbines or oil rigs) Fisheries monitors 	This technology represents an upgrade on an already-used system, and the successful demonstrations in real-world environments using BioCAM on ALR and also Smarty200, at Plocan and at Studland Bay (UK) seagrass (EOV) marine protected area (areas administered by targeted stakeholders) has already started this technology towards active implementation by key users.	9
Optical PhytoPP sensor (MicroSTAF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change, oceanography and planktonic researchers Policy makers and advisory groups with vested interest in climatic and emissions models Marine environmental researchers and conservationists 	The successful demonstrations of the MicroSTAF system was widely well-received by the targeted stakeholder groups, with commercial production systems planned for delivery in 2025. This system will therefore be actively implemented in desired sectors in the near future.	9

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality monitors 		
Bio-assay sensor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquaculture (including coastal and offshore finfish and shellfish farms) • Water services and water quality monitors 	This technology has been demonstrated through the presentation of rigorous tests to key stakeholders in the contaminants monitoring and tracking fields. These assays have been shown to experts to be capable of targeting pesticides, pharmaceuticals and HAB Toxins. These capabilities have been deemed of high policy value due to the growing focus on contaminants of emerging concern and new threats emerging due to warming seas.	5
Biogeochemical dual nutrient sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change researchers and emissions-relevant policy stakeholders • Water and wastewater quality monitors • Coastal aquaculture 	The successful deployment of this system on the AutoSub in Gran Canaria over a full six Southern Mission and the subsequent deployment at the National Oceanography Centre in Southampton has proved highly impressive to peer researchers, government monitors and relevant industry stakeholders. The positive feedback has encouraged the continued development of this technology towards higher TRL, research which is already on track to continue post-project.	6/7
Microcytometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine aquaculture, particularly farms susceptible to harmful algal blooms • Plankton and microplastic researchers 	The deployment of the microcytometer in a field environment, coupled with the data presented showing its impressive depth rating and capabilities for aquaculture monitoring for microplastics and HABs has been well-reviewed by both targeted industry stakeholders and policy experts. This feedback has supported the continued advancement of the technology down the pathway towards sectoral impact.	6

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